

Integrated Energy Conversion Circuit for Piezoelectric Energy Harvesting

(Litar Penukaran Tenaga Bersepadu untuk Penuaian Tenaga Piezoelektrik)

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ABSTRACT

The use of harvesting energy in daily life is no longer a new norm for consumers. Harvesting energy can be obtained from various materials such as piezoelectric, photovoltaic, thermoelectric and others. These sources are derived from nature such as heat, light and vibration. The main source of this study is by using vibration. Vibration is also divided into two types of vibration, namely micro and macro vibration. These energy sources need to be used to generate electricity. The main focus of this study is to design and simulate conversion circuits. There are two parts to the conversion circuit, namely the rectifier circuit and the booster converter circuit. High-power conversion circuits can cause a lot of energy to be consumed. Next, will cause the energy harvested to decrease. The designed conversion circuit should be low power and can reduce the leakage current After conducting the study, there are various topologies that can be used for rectifier circuit and booster converter circuit. The rectifier circuit used in the conversion circuit is the N-MOSFET bridge circuit with a forward bias voltage where this circuit can reduce the leakage current. As for the booster converter circuit, the DC-DC boost booster converter circuit was used. It is capable of increasing the input voltage from the output voltage of the rectifier circuit. The increase result for a circuit without load is 50.1mV while the overall load is 170uV. The difference between load and non-load is 9.986%. Next, the design of the combined circuit between the N-MOSFET bridge rectifier circuit with the forward bias voltage and the DC-DC circuit of the booster booster is increased by 530uV along with the load. While for the combined circuit without load is 4.8mV. The difference between load and non-load is 0.854%.

Keywords: N-MOSFET rectifier; boost converter; piezoelectric; energy harvesting

ABSTRAK

Penggunaan tenaga penuaian dalam kehidupan harian bukan lagi menjadi norma baru kepada pengguna. Tenaga penuaian boleh diperolehi daripada pelbagai bahan contoh nya piezoelektrik, fotovoltaiik, termoelektrik dan lain-lain. Sumber ini diperolehi daripada alam semula jadi seperti haba, cahaya dan getaran. Sumber utama kajian ini ialah dengan menggunakan getaran. Getaran juga dibahagi kepada dua jenis getaran iaitu getaran mikro dan makro. Sumber tenaga ini perlu digunakan untuk menghasilkan tenaga elektrik. Fokus utama kajian ini ialah untuk merekabentuk dan mensimulasikan litar penukaran. Litar penukaran terdapat dua bahagian iaitu litar penerus dan litar penukar penggalak. Litar penukaran berkuasa tinggi boleh menyebabkan banyak tenaga akan diambil Seterusnya, akan menyebabkan tenaga yang dituai berkurang. Litar penukaran yang direkabentuk perlu lah berkuasa rendah dan boleh mengurangkan arus kebocoran. Setelah menjalankan kajian, terdapat pelbagai topologi yang boleh digunakan untuk litar penerus dan litar penukar penggalak. Litar penerus yang digunakan didalam litar penukaran ialah litar jambatan N-MOSFET dengan voltan pincang hadapan dimana litar ini boleh mengurangkan arus kebocoran. Manakala untuk litar penukar penggalak, litar DC-DC penukar penggalak meningkat telah digunakan. Ia mampu meningkatkan voltan input daripada voltan output litar penerus. Hasil peningkatan bagi litar yang tanpa beban ialah 50.1mV manakala bersama beban ialah 170uV. Perbezaan antara bersama beban dan tanpa beban ialah 9.986%. Seterusnya, rekabentuk litar gabungan antara litar penerus jambatan N-MOSFET dengan voltan pincang hadapan dan litar DC-DC penukar penggalak meningkat ialah sebanyak 530uV bersama beban. Manakala bagi litar gabungan tanpa beban ialah 4.8mV. Perbezaan antara bersama beban atau tanpa beban ialah 0.854%.

Kata Kunci: penerus N-MOSFET; penukar penggalak ; piezoelektrik ; tenaga penuaian

INTRODUCTION

Many electronic devices today are able to produce their own power at low cost and easy maintenance. This aspect resulted in increased demand for wireless sensors. This technology is an effective way to replace batteries that often require a risky

maintenance operation, particularly in rural areas. Developing an energy harvesting device is also an significant job of extending battery life.

Energy harvesting or energy heating is the method of extracting a small amount of energy from the environment and turning it into electricity by different energy sources. As shown in (Sarker et al.,

2011), micro-energy harvesters are small electromechanical devices that collect ambient energy and then transform it into electrical energy. So there is macro energy, wind power and solar production, which can produce electricity.

The use of piezoelectric materials is one of the power harvesting techniques used in micro electric applications. Piezoelectric sources can be used to transform ambient vibrations into electrical energy which can be stored and used for other devices. Energy harvesting systems based on piezoelectric devices can generally be described as having three main components: piezoelectric

Figure 1 Component in Energy Harvesting

The rectifier circuit is a circuit where AC signals are converted to DC. It is very essential since most systems use DC signals to work. However, the rectifier half-wave circuit is low relative to input voltage (Sampe et al., 2017). There are three types of wave rectifier; diode bridge rectifier, N-MOSFET bridge rectifier, and MOSFET passive bridge rectifier.

Using a diode rectifier circuit, the forward diode will provide a path where the current flows and connects the inputs and outputs when the input voltage is greater. The main downside of this circuit is its poor performance, which is due to the tension obtained from the diode when forward polarization is achieved. The power applied by the correction circuit can be determined as seen by taking into account two diodes to obtain the current flux, and assuming that all the diodes in the rectifier have the same voltage drop (Szarka et al., 2012). Where it is possible to measure the decrease in front voltage on the diode and the current flowing throughout. Electricity consumption is obtained by comparing the electricity used by high and low side devices (Ramirez et al., 2013).

The alternative is where a MOSFET is replaced by the diode rectifier circuit. In order to allow the MOSFET to act as diodes, gate terminals and drains are connected so that the MOSFET can still be in a saturated region. (Le et al., 2006). If there is a voltage between the drain terminal and the source terminal then the transistor flows into the current.

N MOSFET channels can reduce the power losses significantly. Hence the full-wave rectifier MOSFET is chosen to overcome the drop voltage

devices, electrical energy storage, and electronic control interfaces.

Figure 1 lists the basic components of the energy harvesting system. As in the circuit diagram, there is a transducer used to stream power to the circuit for conversion. The conversion circuit would then transform power and store it in energy storage or known as battery. Power management is used for monitoring and handling power requirements based on the resources available and required. Any electronic charge will reap the benefits of the voltage stored in the storage energy

and also to avoid power loss. Additionally, the N channel MOSFET will charge and exceed the plate capacity of the piezoelectric transducer which results in the transducer loss of existing charges (Dhayabarasivam et al., 2018).

However, for the passive MOSFET rectifier circuit, four discrete MOSFETs are used, namely two P channels (M1 and M3) and two N channels (M0 and M2), As inputs, InA would be inputs, higher than InB, transistors, M1 and M2, connected to output, InA, High Out, and InB connected to Low Out. Instead, InB is related to Low Out and High Out as inputs, higher than InA, transistors, M0 and M3, medium, and InA and InB, respectively (Duque et al., 2019).

Converter booster circuit which uses NMOS to elevate low voltage values. It is a fast switch and can work at relatively high frequencies (Ramirez et al., 2013). The MOSFET is powered by a modulation of the pulse width, which regulates the switching task period to achieve a high voltage output. In addition to the MOSFETs, Scottky diodes and inductors are often used to avoid significant drops in voltage. Pulse width modulation (PWM) parameters to control the task cycle often play an important role in rising voltage.

METHODOLOGY

Introduction

The energy harvesting circuit is simulated by using LTspice XVII with 0.18u CMOS technology TMS model. LTspice XVII is SPICE simulation program, which enables enhanced waveform capture and modeling to facilitate the simulation of analog circuits. Simulations have been performed on the

rectifier circuit and the booster circuit. Simulation results from the rectifier circuit to obtain a circuit that has a low leakage current. While the simulation results of the booster converter circuit to see the ability of the circuit to increase the output voltage. Afterwards, the rectifier circuit and the booster circuit will be integrated and combined with the power generator circuit source. The effect of this combination is to get a higher output voltage than the voltage of the signal.

N-MOSFET Rectifier

Generally, the production of piezoelectric vibrational energy harvesting begins with respect to microvolts, millivolts, and volts. On this circuit the input voltage and frequency are 500mV and 200Hz. This circuit comprises four 10um wide and 0.18um long N-MOSFETs. This circuit is a circuit of full-wave rectifier. In the positive cycle NMOS M1 and NMOS M2 will have a running current while the current will move from NMOS M3 and NMOS M4 in the negative cycle. The capacitor is then used to produce a smooth DC voltage. While the inductor is attached to a capacitor to get the current value. Both the inductor and the capacitor are connected to the diode. Diodes are connected to limit the inductor voltage, as too much voltage can increase the temperature, which can cause damage to the inductor during the process of energy harvesting. The figure 2 shows the N-MOSFET rectifier circuit.

Figure 2. NMOS rectifier

N-MOSFET with RBB

Based on Figure 3, the N-MOSFET bridge rectifier circuit with this reverse back bias voltage is simulated. This circuit must obtain the transducer as input voltage, or piezoelectric input. The bulk of every NMOS connected with negative source which is -0.1V. After several tests, the correct bias voltage value of -0.1V was obtained, and it was found that there was at least small leakage current present.

N-MOSFET with FBB

Based on Figure 4 the N-MOSFET bridge rectifier circuit with the forward bias voltage will be simulated. This circuit will receive the transducer's input voltage, or piezoelectric input. This circuit also uses the same circuit as the circuit in Figure 3 unless

for bulk of each N-MOSFET connected with a positive voltage of 0.1V. Several tests were carried out to achieve voltage values than can prevent current leaks. A voltage value of 0.1V will minimize the current leaks.

Figure 3 Nmos rectifier with RBB

Figure 4 Nmos rectifier with FBB

DC-DC Boost Converter

The booster circuit on the converter has various topologies. Boost DC-DC converters were found to be suitable for project, as they were able to increase voltage. The boost booster converter as shown in Figure 5 can be used to increase and decrease the output voltage. The voltage input to the booster circuit originates from the output voltage of the forward bias voltage rectifier N-MOSFET bridge. The boost converter circuit consists of a modulated MOSFET with pulse width, using n MOSFET channels, inductors, and capacitors. It is a continuation of the MOSFET rectifier and is directly connected to the capacitor as power storage.

Figure 5 DC-Dc Converter

Energy harvesting circuit

The circuit used to complete the energy harvesting system is shown in Figure 6. This is a combination of the N-MOSFET bridge manager circuit with the forward bias voltage and the DC-DC circuit of the boost booster. Only N-MOSFET bridge rectifiers with forward bias voltage are used as they are the least current leakage circuit. It is even a circuit that has a high output power. Figure 6 shows a circuit that has a resistor attached to the circuit as a load to see the circuit's capacity to produce output voltage.

Figure 6 Energy harvesting circuit

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

N-MOSFET Rectifier

Simulation of N-MOSFET bridge rectifier circuit is carried out without load and with joint load. Figure 7 shows the simulation results of a load-free N-MOSFET bridge rectifier circuit. The output voltage increases up to 500ms where the voltage is 81mV. Figure 8. shows the simulation results of a bridge rectifier circuit with load. The voltage is constant after $t = 200ms$ which is 26mV. The difference between the N-MOSFET bridge rectifier circuit with and without load is as much as 11%.

Figure 7 Simulation N-MOSFET rectifier non-load

Figure 8 Simulation N-MOSFET rectifier with load

N-MOSFET Rectifier with RBB

The N-MOSFET bridge rectifier circuit with reversed bias voltage is tested without load and with joint load. Figure 9 displays the effects of simulation of the N-MOSFET bridge rectifier circuit with reversed load-free bias voltage. The voltage from the output rises to 500ms where the voltage is 47mV. Figure 10 shows simulation results of loaded bridge rectifier circuit with reverse bias voltage. The voltage from the processor rises up to 200ms. The voltage is constant after $t = 200ms$ which is 14.8mV.

Figure 9 Simulation N-MOSFET rectifier non-load RBB

Figure 10 Simulation N-MOSFET rectifier with load RBB

N-MOSFET Rectifier with FBB

Simulation with forward bias voltage of the N-MOSFET bridge rectifier circuit is conducted without load and with load. Figure 11 shows the N-MOSFET bridge rectifier forward bias voltage circuit simulation results, with no load. The voltage output rises to 500ms where voltage is 101mV. Figure 12 displays the simulation results of a load bridge rectifier circuit with forward bias voltage. The voltage from the output rises up to 150ms. The voltage is constant after $t = 150ms$ which is 40mV. The difference is 12.2 percent between load and load-free circuits.

Figure 11 Simulation N-MOSFET rectifier non-load FBB

Figure 12 Simulation N-MOSFET rectifier with load FBB

DC-DC Boost Converter

The output of a load-free circuit booster converter has been shown in Figure 13. The output voltage increases up to 500ms. Highest output is 50.1mV. Whereas in Figure 14 the outcome of the simulation of the booster converter circuit with load has been shown. The voltage from the input rises up to 250ms. After $t = 250\text{ms}$ the flat voltage is 170uV. The different percentage of circuit without load and circuit with load is 9.986 percent.

Figure 13 Simulation DC-DC boost converter non-load

Energy Harvesting Circuit

Simulation of the load-free combined circuit with forward bias voltage between the N-Mosfet rectifier circuit and the DC-DC booster converter as shown in Figure 15. The simulation result raises output voltage up to 4.8mV at 500ms. As for the circuit with load, it has shown in Figure 16. The output voltage increases up to 300ms. After $t = 300\text{ms}$ the output voltage is 530uV unchanged. The difference between a load and a load-free circuit is 0.854%. This indicates that the load received does not have effect the voltage.

Figure 14 Simulation DC-DC boost converter with load

Figure 15 Simulation energy harvesting non-load

Figure 16 Simulation energy harvesting with load

CONCLUSION

This research was conducted to make the transducer conversion circuit capable of receiving limited input-generating electricity. Besides using piezoelectric energy to overcome the battery replacement problem, particularly in rural areas which sometimes require a high maintenance process.

Initially, there are different ways of designing a circuit which allows the transducer to receive small generating power. The N-MOSFET bridge rectifier circuit with forward bias voltage has been selected to be combined with the booster converter circuit. This is because the N-MOSFET bridge rectifier circuit design with forward bias voltage is capable of reducing the leakage current. The difference in voltage without load and with load is also high compared to the others which is 12.2%. This shows that despite having a load is still high in output voltage.

The boost circuit used is the DC-DC boost converter that can raise the voltage by 9.986%. This circuit can also store voltage inside the capacitor. After that, the outcome of combining two circuit types, namely N-MOSFET bridge circuit with forward bias voltage and DC-DC booster booster, is 0.854%. This shows that low-power circuits can be

implemented as stated in the main goal.

This research uses LTspice XVII where Mentor Graphic is used in the first research process. There are some disadvantages to using LTspice XVII which causes the simulation performance to differ slightly. The LTspice XVII used cannot perform directly for the integrated layout design. However, Graphic Mentor can be used to perform the continuation research for the integrated layout design.

Besides that, this circuit has a low input voltage which requires the help of a circuit such as a cold starter. Continuation experiments concerning cold starting circuits can be carried out. This circuit will be designed to help when the input voltage is too low. This cold starting circuit will provide an auxiliary voltage injection into the conversion circuit conducted in this research.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to thank Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia for their support. This study was financially supported by Geran Universiti Penyelidikan (GUP-2017-084) Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia.

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